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Received: 25-06-2024 / Revised: 23-07-2024 / Accepted: 25-08-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Air pollution, particularly from vehicular emissions, is a significant public health concern globally, with respiratory disorders being one of its major health impacts. Traffic police, due to their long-term exposure to traffic-related air pollutants, are at an increased risk of respiratory issues. In India, the increasing number of vehicles and inadequate pollution control measures have exacerbated air quality problems, particularly in urban areas (NAAQMS, 1989-1993; GPCB, 2007-2011). Prior studies have demonstrated that vehicular pollutants like particulate matter (PM), nitrogen oxides (NOx), and sulfur dioxide (SO₂) contribute to impaired respiratory function and increased respiratory morbidity (Singh et al., 2009; Verma et al., 2003).

Objectives: This study aims to assess the impact of long-term exposure to vehicular air pollution on the respiratory health of traffic police officers in Ahmedabad, with a focus on key respiratory function indicators such as Forced Vital Capacity (FVC), Forced Expiratory Volume in 1 second (FEV₁), and Peak Expiratory Flow Rate (PEFR).

Methods: A cross-sectional study was conducted involving 100 male traffic police officers aged 20-60 years. Participants were divided into two groups: the exposed group, comprising 50 officers with more than five years of exposure to vehicular emissions, and the control group, comprising 50 officers with minimal exposure, working in administrative roles. Pulmonary function tests (PFTs) were performed using a spirometer to assess FVC, FEV₁, and PEFR. Participants were further divided into smokers and non-smokers to examine the combined effects of smoking and pollution exposure on respiratory health.

Results: The study found that traffic police exposed to vehicular pollution had significantly lower lung function compared to the control group. The FEV₁ levels in the exposed smokers were significantly reduced (1.95 ± 0.27 L) compared to the control non-smokers (2.75 ± 0.35 L), indicating an obstructive pattern of respiratory impairment (Singh et al., 2009; Ingle et al., 2005). The FEV₁/FVC ratio was also lower in the exposed group, particularly among smokers, suggesting compromised lung capacity due to prolonged exposure to pollutants. PEFR values also showed a marked reduction in the exposed group.

Conclusion: Prolonged exposure to vehicular emissions has a significant negative impact on the respiratory health of traffic police, especially in smokers. The study highlights the need for protective interventions, such as regular pulmonary function monitoring and the provision of protective masks, to reduce the health risks associated with air pollution exposure. Urban planning and pollution control measures must be strengthened to mitigate these health hazards in high-exposure occupations (WHO, 2000).

Keywords: Air pollution, respiratory health, traffic police, pulmonary function tests, vehicular emissions, spirometry, occupational health, Forced Vital Capacity (FVC), Forced Expiratory Volume in 1 second (FEV₁), and Peak Expiratory Flow Rate (PEFR).

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Introduction

Air pollution is a growing concern in urban environments, primarily due to emissions from vehicles and industrial activities. The World Health Organization (WHO) identifies air pollution as a significant cause of respiratory diseases, including chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) and asthma [1]. Traffic police are particularly vulnerable to these effects as they spend extended periods in high-traffic areas, often without adequate protection

from pollutants. Air pollutants such as particulate matter (PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀), nitrogen oxides (NOx), sulfur dioxide (SO₂), and carbon monoxide (CO) have been shown to impair lung function and contribute to respiratory morbidity [2].

Previous studies have demonstrated a strong association between prolonged exposure to vehicular pollution and diminished respiratory

health among traffic police. For example, studies conducted in cities such as Hyderabad, India, and Bangkok, Thailand, reported significant declines in lung function and increased respiratory symptoms among traffic police officers [8, 11]. This study aims to examine the respiratory health of traffic police in Ahmedabad by assessing pulmonary function and determining the extent of impairment due to air pollution exposure.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Study Population

This cross-sectional study was conducted among 100 male traffic police officers aged between 20 and 60 years, working in Ahmedabad. The participants were divided into two groups:

- Exposed group: 50 traffic police personnel who have worked in high-traffic areas for a minimum of five years.
- Control group: 50 personnel who had minimal exposure to vehicular pollution, working in administrative roles. The study further divided these groups into smokers and non-smokers based on self-reported smoking history. Written informed consent was obtained from all participants.

2.2 Pulmonary Function Tests (PFT)

Pulmonary function was evaluated using The EasyOne™ spirometer, a non-invasive handheld device used to assess various lung function parameters. The tests measured:

- Forced Vital Capacity (FVC): The maximum volume of air that can be forcibly exhaled after full inspiration.
- Forced Expiratory Volume in 1 second (FEV1): The volume of air exhaled in the first second of forced expiration.
- FEV1/FVC ratio: The percentage of FVC expelled in the first second, indicative of airflow obstruction.

- Peak Expiratory Flow Rate (PEFR): The maximum speed of expiration.

Each participant performed three attempts, and the best result was recorded. All measurements were performed in the morning to avoid diurnal variations. The PFT values were compared between the exposed and control groups, as well as between smokers and non-smokers.

2.3 Data Collection and Analysis

In addition to the PFT results, demographic data such as age, height, weight, and smoking history were collected via a standardized questionnaire. Participants with known pre-existing respiratory diseases or structural deformities of the chest or spine were excluded from the study. Permission from ethics committee was taken.

Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 22. Independent sample t-tests were used to compare pulmonary function between the exposed and control groups. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

3. Results

The primary objective of this study was to assess the impact of air pollution on the respiratory health of traffic police personnel in Ahmedabad. A total of 100 individuals were subjected to pulmonary function tests (PFT), with a division based on exposure to vehicular emissions and smoking history. The results presented below highlight the differences between exposed and non-exposed individuals, as well as smokers and non-smokers.

3.1 Demographic Data

The demographic details of the study population, including age, height, weight, and Body Mass Index (BMI), are summarized in Table 1. The average years of exposure among the exposed group was 7.56 ± 0.83 years.

Table 1: Demographic Details of Traffic Police Officers

Group	Exposure (Years)	Age (Years)	Height (cm)	Weight (kg)	BMI (kg/m ²)
Control (Smokers)	N/A	36.76 ± 1.9	171.4 ± 4.5	72.6 ± 6.2	24.7 ± 1.8
Control (Non-Smokers)	N/A	37.16 ± 2.1	172.1 ± 3.9	73.1 ± 5.7	24.6 ± 2.0
Exposed (Smokers)	7.56 ± 0.83	40.89 ± 1.82	171.2 ± 4.8	74.4 ± 7.1	25.2 ± 1.6
Exposed (Non-Smokers)	7.80 ± 0.67	36.56 ± 2.18	170.9 ± 4.3	73.6 ± 6.4	24.8 ± 1.7

3.2 Pulmonary Function Test (PFT) Results

The pulmonary function parameters analysed include Forced Vital Capacity (FVC), Forced Expiratory Volume in 1 second (FEV1), the ratio of

FEV1 to FVC (FEV1/FVC), and Peak Expiratory Flow Rate (PEFR). The results are displayed in Table 2.

Table 2: Pulmonary Function Test Results

Group	FVC (L)	FEV1 (L)	FEV1/FVC (%)	PEFR (L/min)
Control (Smokers)	3.21 ± 0.36	2.61 ± 0.28	81.3 ± 3.9	426.1 ± 36.8
Control (Non-Smokers)	3.30 ± 0.41	2.75 ± 0.35	83.3 ± 4.1	431.4 ± 42.1
Exposed (Smokers)	2.87 ± 0.41	1.95 ± 0.27	68.0 ± 5.5	338.7 ± 33.6
Exposed (Non-Smokers)	3.05 ± 0.45	2.31 ± 0.34	75.7 ± 4.9	372.4 ± 35.4

The FVC and FEV1 values for the exposed group were significantly lower than for the control group, particularly among smokers. The FEV1/FVC ratio was markedly reduced in the exposed smokers (68.0 ± 5.5%), reflecting an obstructive pattern of respiratory impairment. The PEFR was also notably lower in the exposed group, with smokers showing the greatest decline.

3.3 Graphical Representation of Results

The graphs below shows the FEV1/FVC and PEFR levels across the four groups, indicating the reduction in lung function due to pollution exposure and smoking.

Graph 1: FEV1/FVC amongst Smokers and Nonsmokers of Exposed and Non exposed Group

Graph 2: PEFR amongst Smokers and Nonsmokers of Exposed and Non exposed Group

3.4 Statistical Analysis

Statistical significance was assessed using independent t-tests to compare pulmonary function between groups. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

- **FEV1 comparison** between exposed smokers and control non-smokers yielded a p-value of

<0.001, indicating a significant reduction in lung function among the exposed smokers.

- **PEFR** was significantly lower in exposed smokers compared to the control group (p < 0.01).

4. Discussion

The findings of this study highlight the substantial impact of long-term exposure to vehicular air pollution on the respiratory health of traffic police. This is consistent with the results of previous studies, such as those by the Gujarat Pollution Control Board (GPCB) and the National Ambient Air Quality Monitoring Series (NAAQMS), which have reported deteriorating air quality and its effects on public health, especially in urban settings [1, 4].

4.1 Impact of Air Pollution on Respiratory Health

The results indicate a significant decline in pulmonary function (particularly FEV1 and PEFR) among traffic police exposed to air pollution. These findings align with those of previous studies that identified traffic-related black carbon and other vehicular emissions as major contributors to respiratory impairment [5, 6]. The FEV1/FVC ratio, often used to diagnose obstructive lung disease, was notably lower in exposed smokers, suggesting that these individuals are at increased risk of developing chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) [7].

4.2 Synergistic Effect of Smoking and Pollution

The combination of smoking and prolonged exposure to vehicular pollution exacerbated the decline in lung function, with smokers in the exposed group showing the worst PFT results. This synergistic effect has been well-documented in the literature [9, 10], where exposure to both tobacco smoke and vehicular emissions increases oxidative stress and inflammation in the airways, leading to greater respiratory impairment [11].

4.3 Comparison with Previous Research

Similar studies in India and other countries have reported comparable findings. For example, in a study conducted by the American Thoracic Society on traffic police in Bangkok, Thailand, researchers found a significant reduction in FEV1 among those exposed to high levels of traffic-related air pollutants [11]. The current study reinforces these

observations, with comparable results among the Ahmedabad traffic police.

The World Health Organization (WHO) has long emphasized the need for mitigating exposure to vehicular pollution to prevent respiratory diseases [2]. The results of this study further underscore the importance of adhering to WHO air quality guidelines, which aim to reduce the health impacts of air pollution in urban areas [2].

4.4 Health Implications and Recommendations

The significant reduction in lung function observed in this study highlights the urgent need for public health interventions aimed at protecting the respiratory health of traffic police. These interventions could include:

- The use of personal protective equipment (PPE), such as masks designed to filter out fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5}), during work shifts [5].
- Regular health check-ups to monitor lung function and early detection of respiratory impairment.
- Urban planning initiatives aimed at reducing vehicular emissions in high-traffic areas, such as those outlined in the Air Quality Guidelines by WHO [2].

5. Conclusion

This study provides clear evidence of the detrimental impact of vehicular air pollution on the respiratory health of traffic police in Ahmedabad. The results demonstrate that prolonged exposure to traffic-related pollutants, particularly in combination with smoking, significantly impairs pulmonary function. Protective measures and health interventions are urgently needed to mitigate these risks.

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